

EFFECT OF POLYPYROMELLITIMIDE TOUGHENER ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF KEVLAR FIBRE REINFORCED POLYIMIDE COMPOSITE

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SUMMARY: Advanced fibre reinforced composites requiring sufficient fracture energy absorption capability could be realized by modifying the toughness characteristics of the resin matrix used. Polybis-itaconimide matrix has been toughened by incorporating polypyromellitimide-a semiflexible- condensation polyimide-in the concentration range from 0.5 to 3%(w/w of the matrix) and a kevlar 49 composite with this toughened matrix has been developed. The mechanical properties like tensile, flexural and impact fracture toughness of the kevlar reinforced PBIT matrix composite are determined wherein the matrix contains 0.5 to 3% toughener. The synergism in the mechanical properties is observed at 1 to 1.5 % toughener in the matrix.

KEYWORDS: Polybis-itaconimide (PBIT), polypyromellitimide (PPMD), toughening agents, kevlar fibre.

INDRODUCTION

Increased matrix toughness is a main objective of matrix system development in order to improve composite properties such as delamination resistance, impact response, and fatigue behavior and damage tolerance. The critical design criterion in fibre composite for aerospace application demands sufficient fracture energy absorption capability, particularly in impact loading situation. These fracture toughness characteristics should be accompanied with high strength and stiffness at relatively high temperature. The judicial combination of these properties can be achieved in advanced composites generally by three distinctly different approaches:

- 1) The improvement of intrinsic properties of the composite constituents.
- 2) The proper interphase (i.e. fibre and matrix) control and
- 3) The use of tough matrix materials (e.g. rubber toughened epoxies and thermoplastics)

In order to enhance their fracture toughness, matrices using elastomeric modifier have been explore for the last two and half decades and comprehensive review on these toughening method and the various factors which would affect efficiency of toughness is made recently by Kim and Mai (Ref .1). The concept of combining two or more different materials to obtain a new material with synergistic or additive properties has been widely used in polymer composites and polymer alloys. The functional terminated hydrocarbon rubber has been successfully used to enhance fracture toughness of the brittle epoxy and other resins. A major disadvantage (Ref.2) of using rubber modified thermosetting polymer for enhancing fracture toughness, has been the lowering of the glass transition temperature (T_g) and reduction in modulus of elasticity and tensile strength of modified system. The toughening of matrices like epoxy or modified epoxies have been done by the use of conventional tougheners, however, the toughening of the high T_g matrices requires different approach as the hydrocarbon based tougheners may reduce the thermomechanical properties of these high T_g matrices. Macromolecular Research centre, Jabalpur India has recently demonstrated that high temperature resistant polyimide resin matrix PBIT (Polybis-itaconimide- an addition type polyimide) can be toughened (Ref .3) by dispersing relatively high molecular weight flexible polyimide polymer PPMD (i.e. Polypyromellitimide) within the matrix resin. The improved mechanical properties were observed in carbon fibre composite with this blended matrix. As kavlar-

49 and its variants have been used for the high performance composite, it was desired that this high temperature resistant toughened matrix should be used for kevlar reinforced composite. Accordingly in this study, kevlar-49 fabric reinforced composite with PPMD incorporated addition type polyimide matrix have been prepared and the detailed mechanical characterization involving tensile, flexural and impact strength tests have been made for these composites where in PPMD concentration in polyimide matrix was varied from 0.5 to 3 percent.

EXPERIMENTAL

1. MATERIALS:

Kevlar fibre : Polyaramid fibre (Kevlar-49 of M/s Du Pont,U.S.A.) fabric is two harness satin woven fabric yarn and the same has been used as received. The actual fabric weight is 465 gm/m² .

Polypyromellitimide (PPMD): This material is used in its precursor form i.e. polyamic acid (PAA)– a condensation product of pyromellitic dianhydride (PMDA) and oxydianiline (ODA). It was procured from M/s ABR Organic Ltd., Hyderabad, India and this product is marketed as ABRON S-10, which was a 10% solution in Dimethyl Acetamide (DMAc). The PAA was kept in an airtight container and stored at low temperature (-2^o to 3^oC).

Poly-bisitaconimide (PBIT): bis-itaconimide (BIT) is chain extended by Michael Addition reaction, using P-P' diaminodiphenyl methane. This PBIT its prepolymer form inmarketed as R-750 is by from M/s ABR Organic Ltd., Hyderabad, India. The prepolymer of PBIT is the condensation product of Itaconic Anhydride with P'-P' diaminodiphenyl methane (DAPM) was subsequently chemically imidised and chain extended by Michael Addition reaction using DAPM. The detailed chemical reaction are outlined in Results and Discussion section.

2. COMPOSITE PREPERATION:

A 50% solution of polybis-itaconimide (PBIT) was prepared in DMAc solvent, which was already having different concentration of modifier i.e. PAA. The kevlar fibre - PBIT matrix prepreg in which contains varying concentration of PPMD was prepared by recently developed (Ref.4) phase Inversion Technique using out diffusion, and the maximum solvent (about 85% solvent) was removed by this technique. Seven prepregs with the PPMD concentration level of 0 (neat), 0.5%, 1.0%, 1.5%, 2.0%, 2.5%, and 3.0% in PBIT were prepared. Kevlar fabric was used in composite preparation and composites were made by hand lay up in three pieces steel mould. The fibre weight fraction was kept close to 0.70 in all composite and the curing condition employed was two step heating viz. 200^oC for two hours followed by 250^oC for 2 hours. No pressure was recorded for the mould as only manual tightening was followed.

3. MECHANICAL CHARACTERIZATION:

Tensile strength, elongation and modulus of elasticity were determined according to ASTM D-638 and the flexural strength and modulus were evaluated according to ASTM D-790. The universal Testing Machine of M/s Lloyd instruments (model no. LR 1000K) was used for both tensile and flexural properties determination. Impact toughness as per ASTM D-256-88 was determined. Using Charpy Impact Tester. An average of the values obtained for the five samples was reported here.

4. THERMO GRAVIMETRIC ANALYSIS (TGA):

Dynamic TGA of the samples was performed on Perkin-Elmers Thermogravimetric Analyzer (Mode-TGA-7). Thermograms were obtained for samples of PBIT, PBIT modified with 0.5 to 3%

modifier i.e. PPMD and the heating rate of 20°C per minutes was adopted with temperature range from 50°-800°C. The TGA derived parameters viz. ITD, $D_{(1/2)}$ T and residue content are determined. ITD is the initial temperature of decomposition, $D_{(1/2)}$ T is the decomposition temperature at which the sample is half decomposed, UDT is the ultimate decomposition temperature and the remaining part of the sample at 800°C is the residue content.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

As mentioned earlier a blended matrix has been used here. One component is Polybis-itaconimide (PBIT) resin which is the main matrix and the other component is Polypyromellitimide (PPMD) which is a semi-flexible polyimide macromolecule polyamic acid - a precursor of PPMD and PBIT prepolymer are soluble in common solvent. The common solvent as DMAc has been removed by the phase-inversion technique (Ref.4) which can be remove the observed quantity solvent by out diffusion process. The polyamic acid component vetrifies much earlier than the main matrix. This would result in the uniform dispersion of polyamic acid in PBIT prepolymer during the prepreg preparation stage. There will be two processes will take place during the curing of the matrix at elevated temperature and they are:

1. The crosslinking of PBIT prepolymer as shown in reaction scheme (Fig.1) which also describes the synthesis of PBIT prepolymer.
2. The imidization of the polyamic acid which exist in the form of hydrogen bonded with DMAc is shown in Fig.2.

The blend resulting after curing may be isotropic miscible blend wherein the crosslinking component and flexible polyimide macromolecule are dispersed at molecular level. The two phase blend as matrix has been chosen because the impact strength of matrix polymer may enhance by the incorporation of a flexible polymer as a distinct or molecularly dispersed phase. PPMD - a semi-flexible macromolecule shall act as source of dissipation of energy by their deformation and subsequent transfer of energy at localized manner to the neighboring matrix polymer. One can use more flexible macromolecules to achieve better energy absorption capabilities. Nevertheless PPMD has been chosen despite being rigid to some extent, due to its having high glass transition temperature of over 400°C (Ref.5) and favorable solubility of its precursor in common solvent.

It is, therefore, expected that incorporation of PPMD will not affect the thermal stability of PBIT matrix. This aspect has been established by the TGA analysis of neat matrix and as well PPMD incorporated matrix and the results for the various TGA derived parameters are given in Table 1.

It can be seen from table-1 that the values of initial decomposition temperature of the blend matrix have been enhanced by 50 to 65°C by incorporation of PPMD in the range of 0.5 to 2%. The highest thermal stability has been seen at 1% PPMD incorporated matrix. The values of other TGA derived parameters have also indicated the same trend.

The investigation of physicochemical and mechanical properties of the composites of kevlar and blended polyimide matrix are different in three ways from the one studied by us for the carbon fibre based composites (Ref.3). These two major differences are outlined below:

- 1) The PPMD toughener concentration has been varied from 0.5 to 3% in the present study unlike 0 to 10% in the carbon fibre composites. This reduction in the toughener concentration has been made as we have observed enhancement in the thermal stability has been observed only up to 2% of the toughener. Any further increase in the toughener concentration shall results in the thermal stability more or less equal to that of unmodified.

Table-1: - TGA derived parameter for cured PBIT prepolymer and its PPMD incorporated blends.

S.no.	Designation	IDT (°C)	D _{1/2} T (°C)	UDT (°C)	Residue content (%)
1.	Neat PBIT	411.5	496.1	576.9	36.1
2.	PBIT + PPMD (0.5%) matrix	463.6	549.9	631.8	41.5
3.	PBIT + PPMD (1%) matrix	473.9	565.2	652.1	41.7
4.	PBIT + PPMD (1.5%) matrix	466.6	554.1	633.3	38.5
5.	PBIT + PPMD (2%) matrix	469.5	560.8	643.4	43.0
6.	PBIT + PPMD (2.5%) matrix	412.4	500.0	562.0	40.5
7.	PBIT + PPMD (3.0%) matrix	408.3	479.1	562.4	42.5
8.	Neat PPMD	572.0	-	611.0	58.0

- 2) Kevlar fibres are polyaramid fibres and the aromatic amide functionality of the fibre (especially on surface) could interact with the reactive polyamic acid, which is present as a toughener in the matrix before its curing. The polyamic acid, which is uniformly dispersed in PBIT matrix, may have a tendency to diffuse towards the surface of the kevlar fibre due to better polar-polar interaction. This interaction between surface amide functionality of the kevlar fibre and the reactive amic acid moieties of the polyamic acid is shown in fig.3.

Fig.3: The possible interaction between the surface functionality of kevlar with polyamic acid

- 3) The amic acid-amide reaction product would lead to a crosslinking between these two polymers and will have effect on macroscopic properties of the fibre, which would consequently change the overall macroscopic properties of the composite.

The unique interaction between the toughener and the functional groups on the surface of kevlar fibre will have effect on mechanical properties of the overall composites. The detailed evaluation on the mechanical properties of the kevlar composite with PBIT matrix containing varying amount of PPMD toughener has been evaluated which is intended primarily to see the effect of toughener concentration in the matrix on their mechanical properties. The tensile strength and the tensile modulus are plotted against the PPMD content (%) in PBIT matrix and the results are shown in Fig.4.

Fig. 4 : The variation of Tensile Strength and Modulus of Kevlar Fibre Composite with PPMD Content in PBIT Matrix

The values for both these parameters were found to drop at 0.5% toughener content and both tensile strength and modulus increased significantly at 1.0 and 1.5% PPMD content. In the higher concentration range i.e. between 2 to 3% the values have shown a decline trend. The highest tensile strength was observed at 1.0 % whereas highest tensile modulus was shown at 1.5%. These observations are in agreement with the synergism shown in thermal characteristics at this concentration level. The elongation of the composites have also shown the similar trend as shown in Fig.5

The highest value was observed at 1% PPMD content. The higher value of elongation of these kevlar composites than their carbon fibre counterpart can be attributed to fibre-matrix interface modification by polyamic acid - a precursor to PPMD toughener. The flexural property evaluations of the kevlar-PBIT composites have shown very interesting results as given in fig.6.

Fig.5:PPMD Concentration in PBIT vs Elongation (at break) of Kevlar Fibre Composite

Fig. 6 : The effect of PPMD Content in Matrix on Flexural Strength and Modulus of Kevlar Fibre Composite.

The increase in PPMD content has recorded the overall improvement in the flexural strength and modulus of the composites. 2 to 3 times enhancement in the flexural strength was found at 0.5 and 1% PPMD content and very significant (7 times) change in the value was observed at the PPMD content 1.5%. Subsequent increase from 2 to 3% has resulted in decrease in the flexural strength value. The flexural modulus increased only marginally at 0.5 and 1.0 % PPMD content and it has shot up to almost five times higher value at 1.5 % PPMD content. The flexural modulus values for 2 to 3 % concentrations have shown almost similar trend as shown for flexural strength. The results of the impact fracture toughness are shown in fig.7.

Fig 7 : The effect of PPMD content in PBIT matrix on Impact Fracture Toughness of Kevlar Fibre Composite.

It can be seen that a very marginal improvement of 2 to 5% in impact fracture toughness is indicated at 1.0 to 1.5 % PPMD content.

The overall improvement in the tensile, flexural and impact fracture toughness parameters in carbon composite with PPMD toughened PBIT matrix is quite impressive. The synergism in mechanical properties at the PPMD level of 1.0 to 1.5 % indicates the formation of an alloy of PBIT-PPMD blends. The interesting part of these results is that substantial improvement in the properties (especially in flexural) is realized at a very low PPMD content and it will be beneficial both in terms of the matrix processing and its cost. PPMD is 4 to 5 times more expensive than the primary matrix. The improvement in mechanical properties coupled with enhanced thermal stability of this toughened matrix shall provide the unique matrix for the high temperature resistant kevlar polyimide composite.

CONCLUSION

The kevlar fibre composites are prepared with PBIT matrix toughened with semi flexible PPMD polyimide. The PBIT-PPMD blended matrix has higher thermal stability at PPMD content of 1.0 to 1.5%. The flexural properties of the composites are substantially improved at PPMD content of 1.5% whereas the tensile strength and modulus and impact fracture toughness has shown only marginal improvement. The synergistic improvement in the thermomechanical properties is attributed to the alloy formation in the blend and as well favorable fibre-matrix interphase.

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Fig. 1 : The reaction scheme of synthesis of Polybis-itaconimide prepolymer and its crosslinking.

